

TOMATO BREEDING IN UZBEKISTAN AND STUDY OF TOMATO STRAIN F1 HYBRIDS

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Annotation: This article compares disease resistance, transportability, heat and drought resistance of tomato hybrids and stem tomatoes.

Key words: Standard tomato, Surkhan 142, Taramata, Sevara, Volgogradsky 5/95, TMK-22, hybrid, transport bop, obligata, relief nematode, viral mosaic, line.

Enter. President's Decree No. PQ-20 of November 23, 2021 "On measures to develop family entrepreneurship in fruit-vegetable and viticulture and increase the share of peasant farms in agricultural production" In recent years, agriculture Consistent measures are being taken to reform the industry and introduce market mechanisms to the sector. Today, more than 80 types of agricultural products grown in our republic are exported to 66 countries of the world. In this case, the export volume of fruits and vegetables and leguminous products increased by almost 2 times from 2016 to 2021. At the same time, increasing the planting of export-oriented agricultural crops in the field of horticulture, viticulture, policing and vegetable growing, legumes and oil crops in the areas of land that are being reduced from cotton and grain, as well as by attracting large segments of the population, are effective from these lands. In order to achieve additional growth in the network in exchange for the creation of a system of use, it is necessary to take into account a scientifically based approach and studies.

Stem tomatoes. Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is the most widespread crop belonging to the cruciferous family. It is one of the 15 most important agricultural crops in the world. Tomatoes account for every seventh ton of all vegetables grown in the world, and 80% of processed fruits and vegetables are tomatoes. Tomato fruit is distinguished by its high nutritional value, palatability and dietary properties for the human body.

In Uzbekistan, the temperature rises excessively (50-55C) in the summer months, making it much more difficult to grow tomatoes in open fields and get a higher yield. For this reason, in the following years, the demand of tomato-growing amateur vegetable growers, farmers and farms for stem varieties is increasing. Because the stem varieties have a number of advantages: they hold the seedlings well when they are moved to a new place, they make it possible to work between the plants during the growing season due to the fact that the plant grows upright, the fruits on the plant The plant is distinguished from ordinary varieties by its good protection from the sun, etc. Physiologically, the varieties belonging to this species are more resistant to heat and drought than ordinary varieties. Based on this, for several years, SPE and KITI Surkhondarya scientific experimental station have been paying great attention to the creation of stem varieties of tomatoes and their wide use in production. As a result, tomato varieties Surkhan 142, Taramata, Sevara, Sugdiyona, Marjona and MJ-31 lines were created. Among them, the Surkhan 142 Sevara variety is included in the state register, and the Surkhan 142 variety is planted annually in 250-300 hectares of land in our republic. In order to obtain stem hybrids, in 2017, 4 first generation hybrids were obtained by crossbreeding varieties and lines based on the stem x stem scheme in the hybrid nursery. These obtained F1 Surkhan x Taramata, F1 Taramata x Volgogradsky 5/95, F1 L-31 x Surkhan 142, F1 L-31 x

Sevara, F1 MJ-46x Surkhan 142 hybrids are transportable in 2018-2019, parents in terms of productivity Forms and compared to the comparative F1 Nurafshan hybrid were studied.

According to information, the creation of early varieties and hybrids of tomatoes is of great economic importance and is one of the important areas in selection. The creation of early varieties allows, on the one hand, the cultivation of tomatoes in the northern regions, and on the other hand, it creates conditions for obtaining and exporting the early harvest in the southern regions, providing processing enterprises with raw materials at the same rate. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, it has always been important to create early varieties and hybrids of tomatoes. But this problem has not been solved both theoretically and practically. Based on this, in 16 first-generation hybrids obtained on the basis of crossing early tomato varieties, the development phases such as "germination-flowering", "flowering-early ripening of fruits" and "germination-early ripening of fruits" were studied. The obtained data showed that the duration of the period of "germination - flowering" is passed from generation to generation from negative high dominant to positive dominant. To the crossbreeding combination of the degree of dominance was found to be related. The negative high level of this period was observed in Dar Zavolj'ya x Vir-100 hybrid. An intermediate dominance was observed in the F1 Ion-N x Agro hybrid obtained with the presence of parent forms that differ sharply from each other in terms of this character. In the period of flowering and ripening of fruits, the transmission from generation to generation was from positive dominant to negative high dominant level.

Positive dominance Ion-N x Vir-100, Ion-N x Agro, Vir-100 x Dar Zavolzhyia, Vir-100 x Persei, Novichok x Persei, Utro-2 x Dar Zavolj'ya hybrids, negative high dominance was observed in Lyana x Ion-N, Gruntovy Gribovskyy 1180 x Lyana, Dar Zavolj'ya x Novichok, Novichok x Clava moldovy combinations. The period of germination-early ripening of fruits was observed to be passed from generation to generation in the level of negative high dominance to positive high dominance in the first generation hybrids. Studies have shown that 50% of the studied F1 hybrids are biologically precocious.

Studying the disease resistance of tomato varieties and hybrids. Today, in the process of growing demand for the valuable vegetable product, tomatoes, special attention is paid to its transportability and resistance to diseases among all the quality marks. Since 1994, scientific research has been carried out at the scientific experimental station of the ITI of vegetable crops and potato growing, Surkhandarya, with the aim of creating varieties and hybrids resistant to the transporter nematode. As a result of the researches, resistant to nematode and cladosporiosis, the fruits are transportable, fruitful varieties: "Zakovat", "Sugdiyona", "Taramata", "Bakalavr", "Marjona", "Asiyo", "Sovg'a", "Ofarin" and F1 hybrids were created, such as "Nurafshon", "Sadoj", "Senate", "Magistr", and "Shabnam" early varieties. The most promising varieties and F1 hybrids are undergoing preliminary and selection testing. Among them, the F1 "Nurafshon" hybrid was given for state variety testing in 2010, and the "Zakovat" variety in 2016.

According to the information, the preliminary results of TMK-22, Darkhan, Sevara, Revansh, Agro, Finish, Lojayin F1, Sultan tomato varieties and hybrids are resistant to tomato mosaic virus, Fakhriy, Magnat, L-200-9, Yaqut, Eggplant, It can be seen that Surkhan 142 varieties are resistant to the virus. Thus, in order to create initial materials resistant to viral mosaic of tomatoes, 25 varieties and hybrids were artificially infected with the virus and virus-resistant

varieties were isolated. Since viruses are obligate organisms and reproduce inside the cell, it is almost ineffective to fight against them after the plant is sick.

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